

Enter Keywords / Cat ID...

Search

Login

Catalog

Search

Stats

Help

[Home](#) > [Search](#) >

Search Results

Approximately 6 matching results on 1 page.

Note: You are not currently logged in.

You may have access to more results if you [login](#).

[Search Again](#)

Item Type

Org / Status

Item Summary

Entity (ENT)

ORR

Published Externally

[GT-polygon](#)

Although nesting of sea turtles does occur within the Golfo de Fonseca, it is not as widespread or as common as it is on the outer coast beaches. The most common sea turtle in the gulf is *Lepidochelys olivacea*, which nests year round, with the peak period being June-October. *L. olivacea* is likely to nest on basically all outer coast sand beaches (ESI = 3A or 4) and mixed sand and gravel beaches...

 [InPort XML](#)

Data Set (DS)

PIFSC

Published Externally

[Indonesian and Western Pacific bycatch in SSF and by-catch reduction technology testing](#)

Evidence suggests that Indonesian and Filipino coastal waters provide important foraging grounds for several sea turtle species important to U.S. Western Pacific managed areas and ESA recovery mandates. Continued by-catch and persistent direct harvest of sea turtles in these waters are most likely important factors in the declines of many marine turtle populations in the Pacific such as the Pac...

 [ISO 19115](#)

Data Set (DS)

PIRO

Published Externally

[Longline Observer Data System](#)

LODS, the Hawaii Longline Observer Data System, is a complete suite of tools designed to collect, process, and manage quality fisheries data and information. Guided by the principles of the NOAA Data Quality Act, LODS is the result of the collaboration and cooperation of scientists, data collectors

and information management experts across the NOAA Fisheries Pacific Islands Region. LODS is an...

 [ISO 19115](#)

 Project (PRJ)

PIRO

Published Externally

[American Samoa Longline Observer Program](#)

Deploys fishery observers on American Samoa longline fishing vessels targeting tuna (deep set) to record information on gear, catch information, morphometrics, specimen collection, environmental data and interactions with protective species such as sea turtles, marine mammals and seabirds.

 [InPort XML](#)

 Project (PRJ)

PIRO

Published Externally

[Hawaii Longline Observer Program](#)

Deploys fishery observers on Hawaii longline fishing vessels targeting tuna (deep set) or swordfish (shallow set) to record information on gear, catch information, morphometrics, specimen collection, environmental data and interactions with protective species such as sea turtles, marine mammals and seabirds.

 [InPort XML](#)

 Project (PRJ)

PIRO

Published Externally

[International sea turtle funded projects](#)

PIRO may fund activities for the conservation, protection, and recovery of ESA-listed sea turtle species in international locations. As noted within the U.S. Sea Turtle Recovery Plans, some recovery tasks do not necessarily apply to areas within jurisdiction of the U.S., but must be addressed to recover the species. Tasks in international locations are intended to benefit aggregations of sea t...

 [InPort XML](#)

[About InPort](#) | [Contact](#) | [Release Notes](#) | [System Availability](#) | [Privacy](#) | [Security](#) | [Paperwork Reduction Act](#)

Release 6.0.5

Build FINAL (2025-12-02 18:25 UTC)

